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**MICRO AND MACRO ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS
IN THE MARKETPLACE SHOPEE INDONESIA
INDIARTI AMRIH HANTARI**

Master of Sharia Economics UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan Indonesia

TAMAMUDIN

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan Indonesia

HENDRI HERMAWAN ADINUGRAHA

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan Indonesia

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to analyze the macro and microenvironment of the Shopee Indonesia marketplace. The method used by the author in conducting this research is using qualitative research methods in the form of exploration and literature studies. This research shows that the payment system served by Shopee is complete and easy. Shopee has interesting programs and periodically offers free shipping programs with various variants, thus benefiting sellers and buyers. Shopee is the prima donna marketplace in Indonesia. Shopee has a high dominant value in marketplace competition in Indonesia. In the performance of the Shopee marketplace, the features are easy to understand and use to make purchases and sales. The free shipping feature offered by Shopee attracts sellers and buyers to continue buying and selling online through the Shopee Marketplace. Shopee marketplace has a very good micro and macro environmental analysis and supports the growth and existence of the Shopee application to become the favorite choice of Indonesians in online shopping. From the analysis of competitors, Tokopedia is the strongest competitor marketplace for the Shopee Indonesia marketplace. Marketplace Shopee Indonesia does not have regulatory barriers to develop in Indonesia.

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Keywords: analysis, environment, marketplace, Shopee

Introduction

The rapid development of gadget technology and internet networks has brought new changes in the pattern of people's lives, including in trading activities or buying and selling transactions. E-commerce comes as a new system in the world of trade and business. E-commerce is a new system or paradigm in the business world that changes the traditional way of trading through electronic media by utilizing Information and communication technology. Continuously, virtual markets also known as marketplaces emerge, which become a meeting place between sellers and buyers through gadget and network technology.

Indonesia is a country that has a very potential population to market various goods and services. Some marketplaces that have been present in Indonesia until the

beginning of 2024 include; Tokopedia, Shopee, Bukalapak, and Lazada. Alamin's research at the end of 2023 states that Shopee is the favorite marketplace in Indonesia (Alamin et al., 2023). The research highlights Shopee's dominance as a solid leader in the marketplace realm in Indonesia. As the prima donna of marketplaces in Indonesia, Shopee has both a micro and macro environment. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze how the macro and microenvironment of the Shopee Indonesia marketplace.

Research Methods

The method used by the author in conducting this research is using qualitative research methods in the form of exploration and literature studies. Exploration is done by observing the content of the Shopee marketplace application which can be downloaded from the Google Play store. A literature study is carried out by collecting information from websites and journals of previous research related to the research that the author did.

Results and Discussions

Marketplace Shopee Indonesia

Shopee marketplace application is a mobile shopping center launched in December 2015 by PT Shopee Indonesia. The online shopping platform Shopee declares itself as the champion of shopping from home, the goal is to help Indonesians, in particular, to get their daily needs most safely and easily (Suswanto, 2020) (Waziana et al., 2022). Below is an example of the symbol image display of the Shopee application installed on the Android mobile phone screen.

The payment system served by Shopee is complete and easy. Buyers can make payments through bank accounts, ATM transfers, ShopeePay digital wallets, Indomaret/Alfamart outlets, and COD (cash on delivery). Some of the features found in the Shopee application include 1. Free shipping, 2. COD (cash on delivery) feature, 3. Vouchers and Cashback, 4. ShopeePay and Shopee Koin, 5. Shopee game, 6. Monthly promos. The advantage of using this application is that there is a free shipping feature that makes it easy for buyers to get goods without the need to pay shipping costs. Shopee has interesting programs and regularly offers free shipping programs with various variants, thus benefiting both sellers and buyers.

Recently, the latest features from Shopee are Shopee paylater and COD-Cek Dulu. The Shopee PayLater feature can make it easier for buyers who don't have the funds to still shop at Shopee. Meanwhile, the COD-Cek Dulu feature is a modification or improvement in the COD (cash on delivery) system so that buyers who feel that the items they bought do not match the order can return the goods to the seller. There are also Shopee Live and Shopee Affiliate features that are interesting and allow sellers to reap more potential buyers.

Based on the exploration that the researchers conducted on the Shopee application, the authors can mention several advantages of using the Shopee application, among others; 1) has a dashboard that is relatively easy to understand and use by sellers and buyers, 2) buyers who want to return goods or make returns on purchases can also be facilitated, 3) has a special digital wallet that can be directly replenished, namely ShopeePay, 4) more choices in the procedure for paying for goods, 5) more choices in the facility of shipping services (expedition services). However, according to the author, some things need to be improved by Shopee, namely in terms of advertisements that suddenly appear when the Shopee application is used, this feels quite disturbing in the comfort of using the gadget.

Shopee marketplace is also available in the form of a Shopee Lite application that can be downloaded by users. Shopee Lite is an e-commerce platform that makes it easy for you to shop for various marketplace products online. Unlike the Shopee application, the Shopee Lite application is a lighter version and is suitable for use on mobile phones with smaller data storage specifications. As of 17 March 2023, the Shopee Lite application is only available for Android users version 5.0 and above. You can download the Shopee Lite app on the Google Play Store (<https://help.shopee.co.id/portal/9/article/116407> , accessed on 14 March 2023). There are slight differences in the availability of features available in the Shopee and Shopee Lite apps. These differences can be seen in the table below.

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	Shopee Application	Shopee Lite Application
Features	ShopeePay ShopeeFood Shopee loan service product Digital product Shopee games Shopee video Shopee Live others	purchasing products on the marketplace
Payment methods	ShopeePay SPayLater Cash on delivery Mitra Shopee Alfamart Indomaret AgenBRILink BNI Agen46 Bank transfer / virtual account Credit card / debit Credit card instalments others	

Voucher Type	Voucher Gratis Ongkir Voucher Shopee Voucher Diskon Toko Voucher Cashback Voucher Diskon Shopee video/Shopee Live	Voucher Gratis Ongkir Voucher Shopee Voucher Diskon Toko
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Source: <http://www.shopee.co.id>

Shopee Microenvironmental Analysis

The limitations of the microenvironment that will be discussed in this study are buyers and sellers who join the Shopee marketplace, competitors, and stakeholders (shipping/expedition services).

Shopee is a marketplace that contains a collection of seller accounts and buyer accounts. The seller account can also be used to make purchases at other stores. Likewise, the buyer's account, if in the future he wants to sell an item, can also be used to make a sale.

Maulida's research in 2022 states that Shopee is an alternative means of developing the creative economy during the Covid-19 pandemic. Online marketing strategies carried out through Shopee can help MSMEs survive and thrive during the covid 19 pandemic (Maulida, 2022). Thus Shopee has a good role and can empower the sellers who are members of Shopee to be able to survive in difficult circumstances. Even Shopee can make the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic a good opportunity for sellers who join Shopee.

In Indonesia, 57% of MSMEs consider Shopee to be the marketplace that contributes the largest sales turnover compared to other marketplaces. The percentage values for other marketplaces are Tokopedia (28%), Lazada (6%), Bukalapak (3%), Blibli (2%), and others (3%) (Adilah et al., 2022). This statement corroborates the research results by Alamin (Alamin et al., 2023) which states that Shopee is the prima donna of marketplaces in Indonesia. Looking at this data, it appears that Shopee has a high dominant value in marketplace competition in Indonesia. From this data, it can also be concluded that Shopee's main competitor is Tokopedia.

In Saputri's research conducted in 2023, it was stated that the Tokopedia marketplace became the most popular marketplace with 157.2 million active users in 2022, followed by Shopee with 132.8 million active users in the same year (Saputri et al., 2023). Thus it can be seen that the Tokopedia marketplace is the strongest competitor of the Shopee marketplace. The Tokopedia marketplace in 2022 has more active users than Shopee.

Delivery services as a stakeholder that supports Shopee's operations also play an important role in Shopee's success in gaining a high market share. Shopee and shipping services build a kind of symbiotic mutualism that works well. The free shipping feature found in Shopee can attract buyers and sellers to continue transacting through Shopee. Some of the shipping services that are incorporated or collaborating with the Shopee marketplace in 2024 include; J&T Express, JNE, Sicepat, and Anteraja. The number of shipping expedition services that can be selected is adjusted to the availability of these shipping services at the location of buyers and sellers.

Shopee Macro-Environmental Analysis

The macro-environmental boundaries in this study consist of; social, technological, and regulatory factors.

Palupi's research in 2022 states that Shopee is the platform of choice for Indonesians. The public taste or behavior of Indonesian consumers who are already known to love shopping is a social factor that is very influential on the progress of the Shopee marketplace. Shopee as a marketplace is very appropriate to be present in the Indonesian market, which is a country with a fairly high consumer shopping interest in line with its population.

People's Choice E-Commerce Platform in 2022

Source : (Palupi, 2022) in (Simatupang et al., 2023)

The bar chart above shows that the interest of Indonesians to buy through the Shopee platform is very high and dominates with an acquisition rate of 77%. Followed by Tokopedia which is in second place with 39% and then Lazada is in third place with 25%. From these figures, it can be seen that Shopee dominates the choice of the Indonesian people and has a fairly high acquisition rate.

Shopee's revenue in the first quarter of 2022 was reported to have reached US\$1.5 billion. This figure increased by 64.4 percent and also recorded a gross merchant value (GMV) of US\$ 17.4 billion, an increase of 38.7 percent (Burhan, 2022) (Simatupang et al., 2023). Judging from the number of users and Shopee's turnover which continues to increase from year to year, it indicates that Shopee Indonesia is an example of a successful marketplace and is continuously innovating in various aspects. Technological innovation in the form of sales facilities through a live streaming system to support sales services carried out by Shopee is a strategy that is quite successfully implemented by Shopee Indonesia and can advance members or sellers who join Shopee. The Shopee Live and Shopee Affiliate programs are examples of how Shopee's technological innovations are carried out to be able to compete with other buying and selling platforms that have live-streaming sales features, namely the TikTok platform.

In Indonesia, the Shopee application can be easily installed on user gadgets via downloads from the Android Playstore. Meanwhile, users who want to access Shopee via a computer or laptop can also access this marketplace platform via the website address <http://www.shopee.co.id>. Thus the Shopee Indonesia marketplace can attract more users because it can be accessed easily through various facilities and networks.

Most of the sellers who are members of Shopee are community businesses that are classified as micro, small, and medium enterprises. The Indonesian government opens opportunities for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia to develop fully. Various efforts continue to be made by the government to encourage MSMEs to grow. An example of the government's efforts to make it easier for MSME businesses to develop, namely; the halal labeling program through BPJPH with a free self-declaration system, soft loans for MSME businesses, ease of making business licenses / NIBs for MSME-type businesses. Thus, the existing regulations in Indonesia are quite in favor of MSMEs that have joined the Shopee marketplace.

Regulatory factors that are quite supportive also affect the development of Shopee so that the Shopee marketplace can be more advanced and develop as it is today. In 2023 the Indonesian government issued a regulation in the form of a ban on buying and selling through accounts on the social commerce platform, namely TikTok, while buying and selling through Shopee accounts has no restrictions. TikTok Shop officially stopped its operations starting on 4 October 2023. The decision was issued due to the prohibition of buying and selling activities through TikTok Shop by the Ministry of Trade. The ban is contained in the Minister of Trade Regulation Number 31 of 2023 concerning Business Licensing, Advertising, Guidance, and Supervision of Business Actors in Trading Through Electronic Systems which was promulgated on 26 September 2023. Through Regulation of the Minister of Trade Number 31 of 2023, the Government of Indonesia officially prohibits the merging of social commerce with e-commerce (<https://www.bppk.kemenkeu.go.id/balai-diklat-keuangan-pontianak/artikel/larangan-transaksi-jual-beli-di-tiktok-shop-960535>, accessed on 14 March 2024). Social commerce platforms are only allowed to promote goods or services and are prohibited from providing payment facilities or conducting product trading transactions in the application. Thus, in terms of regulations, the Shopee marketplace in Indonesia has no obstacles to develop in Indonesia.

Conclusions and Suggestion

In the performance of the Shopee marketplace, the features are easy to understand and use to make purchases and sales. The free shipping feature offered by Shopee attracts sellers and buyers to continue buying and selling online through the Shopee Marketplace. Shopee marketplace has a very good micro and macro environmental analysis and supports the growth and existence of the Shopee application to become the favorite choice of Indonesians in online shopping. From the analysis of competitors, Tokopedia is the strongest competitor marketplace for the Shopee marketplace. Marketplace Shopee Indonesia does not have regulatory barriers to develop in Indonesia. The author's advice on the appearance of Shopee advertisements that appear too often feels quite disturbing for user comfort when shopping online.

Bibliography

- Adilah, H. N., Ardyan Novita, V., Sri Lestari, D., & Haibah, F. (2022). Beli Online, Bayar Offline: Cod Shopee Dan Dampaknya Terhadap Mahasiswa Millennial. *Academica: Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 6(2), 205–224. <https://doi.org/10.22515/academica.v6i2.5710>
- Alamin, Z., Missouri, R., Sutriawan, Fathir, & Khairunnas. (2023). *Perkembangan E-commerce: Analisis Dominasi Shopee sebagai Primadona Marketplace di Indonesia*. 6, 120–131. <https://doi.org/10.52266/jesa.v6i2.2484>
- Maulida, U. (2022). Marketplace shopee sebagai alternatif mengembangkan ekonomi kreatif di masa pasca pandemi ovid-19. *Madani Syariah*, 5(1), 33–42.
- SAPUTRI, S. A., BERLIANA, I., BERLIANA, I., & NASRIDA, M. F. (2023). Peran Marketplace Dalam Meningkatkan Daya Saing Umkm Di Indonesia. *KNOWLEDGE: Jurnal Inovasi Hasil Penelitian Dan Pengembangan*, 3(1), 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.51878/knowledge.v3i1.2199>
- Simatupang, S., Susanti, D., Butarbutar, M., & ... (2023). Sistem Pembayaran Cash on Delivery Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Di Shopee. *Jurnal Ilmiah Edunomika*, 08(01), 1–15. <https://www.jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/jie/article/view/10711>
- Waziana, W., Saputra, R. H., Sari, N. Y., Kasmi, K., & Aulia, D. (2022). Pemanfaatan E-Commerce Shopee Sebagai Upaya Peningkatan Ekonomi Ibu-Ibu PKK Pelaku Bisnis. *NEAR: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 1(2), 107–112. <https://doi.org/10.32877/nr.v1i2.433>

<https://www.bppk.kemenkeu.go.id/balai-diklat-keuangan-pontianak/artikel/larangan-transaksi-jual-beli-di-tiktok-shop-960535>
<http://www.shopee.co.id>